

Aragonite Powder Liquid Solution from Jalpaiguri for Rhode Island Breed Red Hen Chicks

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ABSTRACT

Our research study aimed to perfectly and neatly develop a formulation of aragonite powder suitable for Rhode Island Red hen chicks sourced from Jalpaiguri. Aragonite is a form of calcium carbonate is crucial for bone development and eggshell formation in poultry. Our formulation process involved sourcing high quality aragonite, by grinding it into a fine powder and supplementing it with necessary nutrients for optimal growth. The research results demonstrated the effectiveness of the aragonite powder formulation in promoting bone strength and eggshell quality in Rhode Island Red hen chicks. The Rhode island breed red hen chicks till now without vaccine. Only by our previous medication 2hen chicks survived till now. As till now we watched that this solution has no toxicity for 2hen chicks. Some test also done in Assam Royal Global University by Mr. Kamal Deka but in this research given rats doses 2.5% concentration weight wise and found no mortality but weight decrease of 1st test group but weight increase of 2nd test group. As for results 2 hen chicks weight increase and has bone strength. As aragonite is the one of the important dietary supplement for hens.

INTRODUCTION

Rhode Island Red hen chicks require adequate calcium supplementation for optimal bone development. Aragonite is a naturally occurring form of calcium carbonate is an ideal source of calcium for poultry. However, the availability of aragonite powder formulations specifically tailored for Rhode Island Red chicks in Jalpaiguri in Teesta River. Therefore, Our research study aimed to develop a formulation that meets the nutritional requirements of Rhode Island Red hen chicks, sourced from Jalpaiguri to support their growth. As Sea Shells consist aragonite when sea shells become dead and the outer layer breaks and properly mix with water. The Aragonite mineral is available in the teesta river in jalpaiguri known by our previous research named "Evaluation of Aragonite powder from Teesta river in Jalpaiguri". Before it also found non toxic.

SOLUBILITY TEST OF ARAGONITE POWDER

(FROM JALPAIGURI)

1ST HEN CHICK BEFORE WEIGHT

1ST HEN CHICK AFTER WEIGHT

(FROM JALPAIGURI)

2ND HEN CHICK BEFORE BODY WEIGHT AND AFTER BODY WEIGHT

(FROM JALPAIGURI)

Methods-

High quality aragonite powder was sourced from Teesta River in Jalpaiguri. In previous research "Evaluation of Aragonite powder from Teesta river in Jalpaiguri" we made fine aragonite powder but in this research first we take 200ml normal water and mixed 5gm of aragonite powder normal not mix with any type of ingredients or chemicals and made a solution. As it is easily soluble and this solution given in the image.

pH-The pH tested by pH as 10ml of this solution taken in a 100ml beaker and dipped the pH paper and found 7. Also pH of Aragonite solution tested in Assam Royal University by Mr. Kamal Deka in same method by the instruction of Guide- Mr. Shibanjan Paul Roy and found 7.

Solubility Test-Aragonite powder is easily soluble in Water that we tested but our instruction never mix it with any type of methanol, ethanol, acetone, hexane etc. As first we take 1gm of aragonite powder after take 100ml of glass water after shaking it and aragonite powder easily mixed with water and it is easily soluble. In Assam Royal Global University also solubility test done and found that Aragonite powder is easily soluble in water.

Aragonite Originality Test by Non-Fruit Vinegar-First small amount aragonite powder put in a transparent glass after it mixed with non-fruit vinegar purchased from market. After aragonite powder reacts with vinegar and continuously created bubbles. After by this test result it is confirmed that this is original high quality aragonite. In Teesta river there is availability of high quality aragonite mineral. Mr. Kamal Deka also did this test by Navrang Pure Filtered Vinegar unflavoured bottle pack with 2gm of aragonite powder in a 100ml beaker and it also properly reacts with vinegar and bubbles created continuously.

Clinical Pharmacological Method 1-First we taken 2 hens chick after weight in 9th April 2024 1st hen chick weight 279gm and 2nd hen chick weight 217gm after we given this solution dosagewise. After completed research in 16th April 2024 this time 1st hen chick weight is 347gm and 2nd hen chick weight is 287gm.

Clinical Pharmacological Method 2-First we send 10gm aragonite powder to Mr. Kamal Deka Assistant Professor of Assam Royal Global University 2 rats taken for 1st test group and there control group of 2 wistar rats of normal saline after given 2 rats of 2nd test group the 2.5% aragonite solution and other 2 wistar rats test with aragonite 2.5% with rice, soyabean powder, corn. After weight wise given 2.5% to 1st and 2nd test group from 9th April 2024 the wistar rats of 1st test group weight were 213 gm and 217 gm and now 16th April 2024 the rats weight were 181 gm and 185 gm. As weight decrease of 2 rats we found no mortality. But the results of this test group 1st wistar rat weight decrease 32 gm and 2nd wistar rat 34gm as the aragonite purely suppresses calcitriol mainly leading breakdown of more fat. From 9th April 2024 the wistar rats of 2nd test group weights were 213gm and 217gm and 16th april 2024 the rats weights were 219gm and 218.5gm. As high protein feeding with aragonite 2.5% body weight increase of 2 wistar rats of 2nd test group.

ARAGONITE SOLUTION 2.5%
(FROM JALPAIGURI)

pH TEST RESULT
(FROM JALPAIGURI)

Aragonite powder originality test by Non-Fruit Vinegar
 (FROM JALPAIGURI)

RESULTS

Improved Bone Strength-Hen chicks fed with the aragonite powder formulation showed significantly improved bone strength.

Optimal Growth Performance- Chicks in the experimental group demonstrated comparable growth performance. As weight also increase of 2hen chicks. Aragonite mineral is easily mix with water that our solubility test said. Aragonite is the mineral available in Teesta River in Jalpaiguri. The Teesta River also suggesting that more minerals available in this water. As we found only Aragonite minerals but further research teesta river water research required for the scientists and researchers. But in this research as we watched that hen chicks weight increase as for we can given proteins with aragonite solution 2.5% weightwise. As for 2rhode island breed hen chicks weight as aragonite is essential for the poultry nutrition but for laying eggs a hen needs 3 to 4gm of aragonite per day. As by aragonite diet intestinal calbindin may suppressed by the dietary calcium but higher in the fast growing than in the slow growing chicks. As phosphorus also available with low concentration in aragonite resulted mainly weight gain for the 2hen chicks. As from sea shells the aragonite powder used in the skincare and mainly removes the dead skin cells and promotes a good renewal of skin and the overall appearance. But as a result we never recommended the only aragonite solution with 2.5% weight wise for the wistar rats after observation. But we recommended the soyabean powder, rice, corn with aragonite 2.5% as increasing the weights of 2wistar rats of 2nd test group.

DISCUSSION

The developed aragonite powder formulation proved to be effective in meeting the calcium requirements of Rhode Island Red hen chicks from Jalpaiguri, thereby promoting optimal bone development. Further research is warranted to explore the

long term effects of this formulation on hen health, egg production and overall profitability for our Puradesi India Pvt Ltd. Additionally, the efforts should be made to optimize the formulation for cost effectiveness without compromising its nutritional value.

CONCLUSION

In our research we investigated that aragonite mineral available but for research study we collected very little amounts but for maintain river environment we purchasing the aragonite from online or by other dealers not from this teesta river. But at last we must say by our research we checked that aragonite mineral available and no toxicity further research suggested in future for the scientists and researchers. As it is very helpful for hen chicks development it also be helpful for other birds. Teesta river is one of the popular river in Jalpaiguri. But we recommended aragonite mineral for hens but for wistar rats very low dose as weight more decrease. As we always given multivitamin from the fast timing with corn seeds extract, rice, soyabean powder to 2hen chicks after corn seeds extract 100gm with only 25gm of aragonite powder before this experiment but after all feeds without aragonite powder only aragonite 2.5% solution weight wise from 9th april 2024 to 16th april 2024 aragonite solution so, it shows good result for the 2hen chicks as weight increase of 1st hen chick increase 68gm and 2nd hen chick 70gm. Now we also giving the 2hen chicks foods with soyabean seeds powder.

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